

KICK-OFF MEETING MINUTES

SUBJECT	B-THENET Kick-off Meeting
LOCATION	Food and Agriculture Organization of the United Nations -FAO
DATE	15-16 September 2022
MINUTES	IZSLT, APRE / Contribution from all Consortium

Welcome to participants

FAO and IZSLT welcome the Participants to the Kick-off Meeting.

No questions/comments.

Project management and monitoring from REA

The Project Advisor analyses the B-THENET context in the Horizon Europe Programme. Moreover, she highlights the more interesting provisions in the Grant Agreement that the Coordinator and the Beneficiaries are required to respect. Finally, she focuses the attendees' attention on the communication, dissemination and exploitation responsibility to maximise the project impact looking also after the project's life.

Question/comments:

- UCM: After the end of the project, for how many years should the papers, and documents be stored?

A.5 years after the final payment

- BEELIFE: Would the Commission financial services accept the digitalised version of all the tickets and expenses incurred during the project duration or linked to the project activities? In this way, we do not need to keep paper support of the expenses; digital format is sufficient and more environmental-friendly.

A. Project Advisor will ask the financial officer in REA and she will report us their consideration.

- BEELIFE: Will all costs incurred in the development of the project be eligible, even those happening outside of the project duration (e.g. tickets bought for the participation at the Kick-off meeting)?

A. Project Advisor will ask the financial officer in REA and she will report us their consideration.

Roundtable-Presentation of Beneficiaries

Questions/comments

- DIMITRA: Will the Beneficiaries' presentation slides be shared with the Consortium?
A. Yes, IZSLT will share the slides and the other main documents of the project on a shared file. Afterwards, the slides will also be shared on the B-THENET website as soon as the last will be ready.
- IZSLT: what is the methodology chosen for the Advisor training activities?
A. SLU will provide the international training of advisors in beekeeping, production of guidelines for advisory services in beekeeping and the Open Educational Resource for training of advisors in beekeeping. The experience of SLU is demonstrated by the existing RådNu, a common competence platform that helps to strengthen the entire knowledge system; agricultural and rural entrepreneurs, advisors, authorities and researchers. SLU will adapt the training activities to the national advisors' knowledge, cultural and professional background, and geographic context. SLU doesn't consider implementing one model of activities but will adjust the TN methodology to the advisor's needs.

WP1 TN Coordination and Management

Project overview, Objectives, Partnership, Flow Chat

Question/comments:

- The Coordinator will inform on the modalities to share the financial supporting documents for the periodical reports.
- Project Advisor: the project should take care of the risks identified in the Annex 1 of GA and we should maximize the impact of the project emphasizing the dissemination, communication and exploitation activities.

Platforms

Comments:

- Platforms will be easily accessible from BTHENET project website.
- The R&I and Practices Platforms will be available for the Beneficiaries, Advisory Board Members and Collaborating Partners.
- The visitors can register on the Exchange platform and a panel of moderators will be set up to moderate the Exchange and Repository Platforms.
- The Platform are "logically" divided but stored on the same server (that will be in EU). A filter option will be available in the Platforms.
- The hosting of the Platform is under the ownership of the Coordinator.
- BEELIFE: we can also develop a beekeeping dictionary.

Question:

- DIMITRA: There is a limit for comments as well as the visitors' interaction?
A. A panel of moderators will build up and manage the interactions inside the Platform using a democratic methodology.

Task, Action plan

No questions/comments

WP2 Collection and Evaluation of Practices

Comments:

- There are many entities committed to building a Community of Practices in the beekeeping sector (for instance, the EU Bee Platform). The Consortium's idea is to support these Entities analysing their methodology and the result but, at the same time, B-THENET should build up its own identity.
- Regarding the stakeholder engagement activities (Task 2.1), IZSLT and BEELIFE will search for International Conferences (e.g. APIMONDIA SYMPOSIA) and events (e.g. CS meetings) to try to organize common action or uptake the B-THENET results and methodology.

Questions:

- BEELIFE: How and when we should set up the information structures? A working group will arise to define the procedures, structure (like a Standard Operating Procedure template) and databases (an interaction with Apimondia BEEXML Working Group is foreseen).

WP3 -Validation of Practices

Comments:

- LBTU: The activities of validation will be carried out by templates/surveys whose results will be shared with the Consortium on the platforms.
- BIAVL: we should address a simple model of validation to reduce the time of stakeholder engagement.

WP4 – Dissemination, Communication and Exploitation

Question/comments:

- The DCE Activities will require the involvement of all Beneficiaries. More in details, for the translation of DCE materials, APRE or another WP4 Partner will send the standard English version of a text (articles, infographics, video etc) to the Partners to translate into their native language.
- UGRAZ and UHOH will prepare a standard article for beekeeping magazines to present B-THENET.
- BIALV: Why have we chosen to translate into fifteen languages? We will translate into 15 languages considering the number of languages spoken in the Consortium
- We will use software like Google Translate and Deepl to support us in the translation activities
- All Partners are kindly invited by the Coordinator to start working at the National B-THENET centres, involve the respective Collaborating partners and update them on the B-THENET activities.

Wrap up: definition of Action of the project for the next 6 months

Question/comments:

- In the next weeks, the Coordinator will receive invitations from WP leaders to organize meetings to implement the B-THENET activities. The presence of Collaborating Partners is strongly suggested.

- We will use SLACK for internal communication (e.g to organize meetings or avoid disproportionate use of emails). Emails will only be used to share important documents (e.g. deliverables, milestones, monthly meetings). The subject of emails should always contain “B-THENET” as start text.
- The Coordinator suggests the use of the Cisco Webex Meeting teleconference software as it will be possible to have unlimited users, time and recordings for the teleconference. To request a teleconference, the Coordinator or the Partner can send an email to the B- THENET internal email address with date, hour, duration, emails of participants and agenda. An automatic email with meeting details will be sent from this email. The Coordinator or the Partner will moderate the meeting and will prepare the minutes that will be sent to the Coordinator and the Consortium.

Annex 1 – Deliverables, milestones and main activities for the next 6 months

WORKPACKAGE 1 – TN Coordination and Management

Due date	Deliverable n.	Title	Leader
30 September 2022	D1.1	Kick-off meeting report	IZSLT
30 November 2022	D1.5	Risk Management Plan	APRE
31 December 2022	D1.6	Ethical issue	APRE
28 February 2023	D1.7	Data Management Plan	APRE

Monthly teleconference meetings will be organized by APRE.

WORKPACKAGE 2 – Collection and Evaluation of Practices

Due date	Deliverable n.	Title	Leader and co-leader
31st of October	D2.1	Strategy to build a Community	BEELIFE, with support of all partnership
31 January	D2.22	Methodology definition for the analysis of practices	LLU (lead); IZSLT, UGRAZ, SLU (co-leaders)

Community building: starting from contacts obtained by Beneficiaries, Collaborating Partners, Advisory Board members (e.g. COLOSS), B-GOOD project, etc...

Set-up of a scientific methodology to evaluate the practices (cost-benefit, readiness, time to dedicate, sustainability, scientific value, etc.): please, LLU, start doing proposals to IZSLT, UGRAZ, SLU.

WORKPACKAGE 3 – Validation of Practices

No deliverables are foreseen for the next 6 months. But organization could already be set-up/start!

Please, BIAVL, start providing an Excel file to collect info about the National B-THENET Centres (e.g. place of each Centre, available seats for meetings, names of persons depending by specific skills -e.g. educators or moderators, number of hives that could be potentially available etc.).

WORKPACKAGE 4 –Dissemination, Communication and Exploitation

Due date	Deliverable n.	Title	Leader and co-leader
31st of January	D4.1	Plan for dissemination and exploitation including communication activities	APRE

Subgroup platforms: relate to Coordinator.

Beneficiaries or Collaborating Partners that already have a website available (e.g. honeybeevalley.eu) or have communication activities already ongoing, please relate with LOBA/IZSLT/APRE to verify possible synergies for the platforms (e.g. similar or complementary structure; similar communicating approach, etc.). The same for the set-up of the educational website for Advisors.

Dissemination: please, keep in mind even that it could be useful to disseminate in citizen science meetings or similar meetings for advisors or beekeepers; as well as make an inventory of beekeeping journals to contact.

